

Synthesis, Characterisation and Reactivity of Copper(II)-amine Complexes bound to Support—an Inorganic Ion-exchanger Zirconium Tungstate

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Cu^{II}-amine complexes have been supported on to the surface of an inorganic ion-exchanger zirconium tungstate. Coordination behaviour of the complexes bound to zirconium tungstate have been studied by TGA DSC FTIR ESR and reflectance spectra. The catalytic activity has been studied through the disproportionation of hydrogen peroxide. Activation parameters have been calculated. The order of the activation parameters obtained have been explained on the basis of a Jahn-Teller distortion in Cu^{II} complexes

The supported metal complex catalysis is an area of intense current interest¹. Complexes have been affixed to polymers² formed in zeolite cavities³ and affixed to silica or alumina surfaces⁴. Recently, bulky complexes have been incorporated between the layers of a smectite clay (hectorite) by an ion exchange process and these products have exhibited interesting catalytic behaviour⁵.

Hydrogen peroxide participates in a variety of chemical reactions⁶. The metal ion catalysed disproportionation of H₂O₂ has received much attention, which is mainly stimulated by the natural occurrence of a heme iron enzyme i.e. catalase, which enhances the decomposition dramatically⁷,

The above reaction is also catalysed by Cu^{II} complexes provided the coordination sphere is accessible for H₂O₂ and/or HO₂⁻⁸. Among the active complexes are the 2,2'-bipyridyl containing species [Cu(bipy)]²⁺⁹ and *cis*-[(H₂O)₂Cu(bipy)₂]²⁺^{10,11}. [Cu(bipy)]²⁺ also exhibits a peroxidase like activity¹², as does *cis*-[(H₂O)₂Cu(bipy)₂]²⁺ and the reaction proceeds in all these cases within the coordination sphere of the metal ion^{9-11,13}.

The synthesis and ion-exchange properties of zirconium tungstate have been studied earlier^{14,15}. To date, no work has been undertaken to examine the catalytic property of these compounds.

In the light of enhanced activity of heterogenised homogeneous catalysts, the present work pertains to the study of catalytic activity of a typical heterogenised homogeneous system. Zirconium tungstate, an inorganic ion-exchanger has been used as a support on which [Cu(NH₃)₄]²⁺, [Cu(ethylenediamine)₂]²⁺, [Cu(en)₂]²⁺, [Cu(1,2-diaminopropane)₂]²⁺, [Cu(1,2-pn)₂]²⁺ and [Cu(2,2'-bipyridyl)]²⁺, [Cu(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ have been anchored. Coordination behaviour of these complexes bound to zirconium tungstate has been studied by TGA, DTA, ir, esr and reflectance

spectra. The catalytic activity has been studied through the disproportionation of hydrogen peroxide. Activation parameters have also been calculated. Comparative coordination tendencies of these complexes on solid support has also been discussed.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis indicates the composition of zirconium tungstate, Zr : W to be 1 : 2.

TGA of zirconium tungstate indicates the presence of about 20% hydrated water which is lost very slowly within the temperature range 80–180°. There is no evidence for the decomposition of the solid within 1000°. TGA data of [Cu(NH₃)₄]²⁺, [Cu(en)₂]²⁺, [Cu(1,2-pn)₂]²⁺ and [Cu(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ supported on zirconium tungstate show additional break within the temperature 290–320°, 300–330°, 320–360° and 340–380° respectively, which may be due to the decomposition of the complexes.

DTA of zirconium tungstate shows only one exothermic peak at 120° indicating the presence of water. There is no endothermic peak upto 500°, which indicates that there is no phase change. DTA data of [Cu(NH₃)₄]²⁺, [Cu(en)₂]²⁺, [Cu(1,2-pn)₂]²⁺ and [Cu(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ supported on to zirconium tungstate show two additional exothermic peaks at the same temperature range as mentioned in TGA earlier. This may be due to the decomposition of the complexes. In all the four cases, there is no endothermic peak, which indicates that there is no phase change.

The ir spectra of the support (zirconium tungstate) show broad bands at ~3 400 cm⁻¹, which is attributed to asymmetric and symmetric hydroxo-(OH) and aquo-(OH) stretches. A sharp medium band at ~1 620 cm⁻¹ observed is attributed to aquo-(H-O-H) bending. Ir spectra of the samples also give an idea about the presence of complexes on the support. However, a quantitative interpretation

is not possible due to strong coupling between various vibration modes.

[Cu(NH₃)₄]²⁺ supported on zirconium tungstate shows broad bands at ~3 300 and ~1 640 cm⁻¹. This may be attributed to merging of OH and NH stretching and OH and NH bending modes respectively.

In case of [Cu(en)₂]²⁺ and [Cu(1,2-pn)₂]²⁺ supported on zirconium tungstate, additional bands are observed at ~2 900, 1 450 and 1 260 cm⁻¹, which correspond to aliphatic C-H stretching, wagging and deformation of CH₂ group respectively. It also shows broad bands at ~3 300 and ~1 640 cm⁻¹, attributed to merging of OH and NH stretching and OH and NH bending modes respectively.

Ir spectra of [Cu(2,2'-bipy)]²⁺ bound to zirconium tungstate show bands at ~3 040 (aromatic C-H), ~1 600 (C=C and C-H), ~1 200 (C-C) and ~1 150 cm⁻¹ (C-H).

In order to further confirm the presence of complexes on surface of the support, samples were run for reflectance and ESR spectra.

The reflectance spectral data of the support and the complex bound to support are presented in Table 1. Shift in λ_{max} positions may be attributed to a slight distortion in the geometry around the Cu-centre due to the sorption of complexes on zirconium tungstate. Such distortions from the original geometry has been observed in case of complexes bound to other supports¹⁶.

TABLE 1—REFLECTANCE AND ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES AND THE COMPLEXES BOUND TO SUPPORT

Parameter	[Cu-(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺	[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺	[Cu-(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺	[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺
λ _{max} for complex	600	590	530	675
λ _{max} for complex bound to support	720	660	560	700
g _{av} for free complex	2.126	2.064	2.063	2.076
g _{av} for bound complex	2.116	2.030	2.030	2.073

The esr spectra of the complexes sorbed on zirconium tungstate are similar to those of free complexes in solid state. The g_{av} values (Table 1) of bound complexes are slightly less as compared to those in the free complexes. This indicates that there is only a slight increase in the crystal field around the central metal ion when the complex is sorbed on to the support. This shows that there is not much change in geometry of the support bound complexes compared to the free complex. Similar observations were also made earlier¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

The surface area data of the support and complex bound to the support are presented in Table 2. As compared to support there is an increase in the surface area of complex bound support.

The characterisation of the complexes indicates that there is no change in geometry of the supported

TABLE 2—SURFACE AREA OF SUPPORT AND COMPLEXES BOUND TO SUPPORT

Compd	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹
Zirconium tungstate (ZW)	15
[Cu(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺ -(ZW)	158
[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺ -(ZW)	143
[Cu(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺ -(ZW)	130
[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺ -(ZW)	115

metal complex as compared to the free complex, thus making it a suitable material for the study of heterogenised homogeneous catalysis. In the present investigation, the kinetic analysis is based on the initial rate data because the reaction rate approaches equilibrium after a lapse of time.

The rate was found independent of initial concentration of H₂O₂ (Table 3a). An increase in the amount of catalyst increases the rate of reaction, (Table 3b) indicating that there is no dimerisation of the metal complex in heterogenised system in the range studied. Increase in the temperature of the system increases the rate of the decomposition (Table 3c).

TABLE 3—CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF COMPLEXES SORBED ON SUPPORT

(a) Influence of H ₂ O ₂ Concentration at 35° (Catalyst=0.05 g)		
Complex	Concn. of H ₂ O ₂ (vol)	10 ⁴ k (min ⁻¹)
[Cu(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺	5.00	5.55
	7.50	5.60
	10.00	5.70
[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺	5.50	1.30
	7.50	1.02
	10.00	1.15
[Cu(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺	5.00	2.40
	7.50	2.30
	10.00	2.30
[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺	5.00	9.36
	7.50	9.77
	10.00	9.97
(b) Influence of Catalyst Quantity on Decomposition of H ₂ O ₂ at 35° (H ₂ O ₂ =10 ml (4 vol))		
Complex	Amount of complex on support 10 ⁻² g	10 ⁴ k (min ⁻¹)
[Cu(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺	3.16	1.76
	6.32	3.37
	9.48	4.93
[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺	1.42	0.70
	2.84	1.22
	4.26	1.61
[Cu(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺	1.83	0.5
	3.67	1.1
	5.50	1.3
[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺	2.15	4.76
	4.30	10.20
	6.45	12.20

Table—3 (Contd.)

 (c) Influence of Temperature on Decomposition of H_2O_2
 (Catalyst=0.05 g ; H_2O_2 =10 ml (4 vol.))

Complex	Temp. (°C)	$10^4 k$ (min ⁻¹)	E (kcal mol ⁻¹)
[Cu(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺	25	2.44	14.76
	30	3.83	
	35	5.70	
	40	7.20	
[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺	25	6.6	11.0
	30	8.7	
	35	12.4	
	40	18.0	
[Cu(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺	25	1.34	13.0
	30	1.60	
	35	2.30	
	40	3.49	
[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺	25	5.18	10.00
	30	6.21	
	35	8.95	
	40	12.00	

The colour of the surface adsorbed complex ion was observed to change from blue to greenish yellow when it came in contact with H_2O_2 . The colour persisted as long as any residual H_2O_2 remained undecomposed. After complete decomposition of the H_2O_2 , the catalyst regained its original blue colour. Similar results were observed by Ram *et al.*^{19,20} in the decomposition of H_2O_2 using metal complexes supported on silica or alumina as catalysts. This could be due to the formation of a peroxo species^{21,22}.

Based on the above observations, the following reaction mechanism and rate equation have been suggested, as proposed by us earlier²³.

It is known that H_2O_2 dissociates to

The surface $[Cu(L)_2]^{2+}$, where L=ammonia, ethylenediamine, 1,2-diaminopropane and 2,2'-bipyridyl, may interact with HO_2^- ion to form an intermediate complex,

A second molecule of H_2O_2 may then interact with the intermediate complex to form the products,

During the course of the decomposition of H_2O_2 , there is a continuous increase in pH which confirms

the liberation of OH^- ion as per the suggested mechanism.

In the present study, the order of stability of the complexes is $[Cu(2,2'-bipy)]^{2+} > [Cu(1,2-pn)_2]^{2+} > [Cu(en)_2]^{2+} > [Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$. This has been determined based on the stability constant values²⁴. Dipyriddy complex is strongest due to π -interaction²⁵. In $[Cu(1,2-pn)_2]^{2+}$ and $[Cu(en)_2]^{2+}$, both form five-membered rings. But stability of 1,2-pn is greater because of an electron-donating methyl group present on the carbon. $[Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$ is least stable because it just forms a simple complex.

The activation energies (E) calculated from the Arrhenius plots (Figures not shown) obtained for the copper complex, sorbed on zirconium tungstate in the decomposition of H_2O_2 is in the sequence, $[Cu(2,2'-bipy)]^{2+} < [Cu(en)_2]^{2+} < [Cu(1,2-pn)_2]^{2+} < [Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$. Normally, more stable complexes should give higher E and lower K values. However, the results (Table 4) indicate higher K values with higher E values. This suggests that the reaction rate is governed by an entropy of activation²⁶. The ΔS^\ddagger value (Table 4) increases in the following order: $[Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+} > [Cu(1,2-pn)_2]^{2+} > [Cu(en)_2]^{2+} > [Cu(2,2'-bipy)]^{2+}$. The greater the value of ΔS^\ddagger , greater is the value of K and greater the probability of activated complex formation. The order of the values of E , K and ΔS^\ddagger could be attributed to Jahn-Teller distortion in the Cu^{II} complexes.

It is known that in Cu^{II} complexes due to Jahn-Teller effect, there is axial distortion and the z -axis is far off compared to x - y axis. Greater the stability of the complex, greater is the axial distortion. This means that the $Cu-N$ bond distance is lower in case of $[Cu(2,2'-bipy)]^{2+}$ and highest for $[Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$. In other words the bipyridyl molecule is closest to the Cu^{II} ion and furthest in case of NH_3 molecule. The extent of elongation distortion is therefore greater in case of the bipyridyl complex.

For the present complexes anchored on to the surface of support, four equatorial positions are occupied by ligands. Out of the two axial positions, one interacts with the support while the other position (sixth) remains vacant for the attack by H_2O_2 molecule. Since the axial position is at a greater distance in case of $[Cu(2,2'-bipy)]^{2+}$, there is not much steric crowding during H_2O_2 attack. This may not be so in case of $[Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$, where the

 TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR Cu^{II} -AMINE COMPLEXES BOUND TO THE SUPPORT

Complex bound	Temp. = 35°				
	K min ⁻¹	E kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
[Cu(NH ₃) ₄] ²⁺	3.32×10^{-4}	14.76	9.00	14.14	17.31
[Cu(1,2-pn) ₂] ²⁺	1.10×10^{-4}	13.00	9.10	12.38	10.67
[Cu(en) ₂] ²⁺	1.22×10^{-4}	11.00	9.36	10.38	3.58
[Cu(2,2'-bipy)] ²⁺	10.20×10^{-6}	10.00	9.40	9.38	2.00

axial distance is comparatively shorter. However, in case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(1,2\text{-pn})_2]^{2+}$, there is a reversal in the order. This could be explained to be due to the fact that the ease of exchange in case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$ is greater as compared to $[\text{Cu}(1,2\text{-pn})_2]^{2+}$. This is probably due to the bulky methyl group present in 1,2-pn. This is confirmed by the fact that the amount of $[\text{Cu}(1,2\text{-pn})_2]^{2+}$ sorbed per g of support is much less as compared to $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$. This fact explains the order of values of energies of activation.

The values of energy of activation suggests that the Cu^{II} complexes sorbed on zirconium tungstate are catalytically active. The activity of the complex ions in the decomposition of H_2O_2 may be explained on the basis of the formation of a stable ternary complex between the Cu-complex and an oxygen donor. In other words, the activity may be attributed to the formation of an intermediate peroxy species. Besides, when a metal complex is bound onto a support its motion is restricted. Reactions on such catalysts are expected to be more rapid than one in which the catalyst molecules are free²⁶.

The activity of surface anchored complex is dependent on the availability of sites present on the surface of the support. Thus, on increasing the amount of catalyst, the rate constant should increase, which has been found so as revealed by the data (Table 3). It has been observed earlier by other workers²⁷ that the catalytic activity increases with increase in surface area. Higher surface area of Cu-complex bound to support as compared to that of the support may be another reason for higher catalytic activity in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.

Experimental

Preparation of support (zirconium tungstate): Aqueous solutions of zirconium oxychloride and sodium tungstate were mixed till complete precipitation. The gel was digested at room temperature for several hours, washed with conductivity water to remove excess chloride, filtered and dried at 100°. For kinetic studies the gel was broken down to the desired particle size and sized. It was converted to the hydrogen form by immersion in 1 M HCl, then washed with conductivity water, filtered and dried at 100°.

Anchoring of complex cations on to the support: A known amount of the complexes were dissolved in 25 ml of conductivity water to prepare 0.05 N solution of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cu}(1,2\text{-pn})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(2,2'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$, by a known method²⁸. To the acid treated ion-exchanger (1 g), the above complex ion solution was added, and then kept for 24 h with intermittent shaking. It was filtered, washed with conductivity water till complete removal of adhering complex and dried at 100°. All washings were collected along with filtrate to determine the quantity of remaining Cu^{II} ion and

the concentration of Cu^{II} ion present on the exchanger was calculated by difference.

The sample was analysed for zirconium and tungsten²⁹. Copper was determined iodometrically in case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cu}(1,2\text{-pn})_2]^{2+}$ and spectrophotometrically for $[\text{Cu}(2,2'\text{-bipy})]^{2+}$ supported on ion-exchanger.

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on a Shimadzu DT 30 analyser at a heating rate of 10°/min. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Shimadzu IR 408 spectrophotometer, reflectance spectra on a Shimadzu PR-I spectrophotometer using BaSO_4 as reference and esr spectra (at room temperature) on a Varian E-15 spectrometer, g_{av} values being relative to TCNE standard with $g=2.00277$.

Surface area measurement was done by nitrogen absorption BET method.

Kinetic studies: A weighed quantity of complex bound zirconium tungstate was shaken with H_2O_2 (10 ml; 4 vol) in a thermostat (25°). The desired concentration of H_2O_2 was obtained by successive dilution from the stock solution. The volume of oxygen evolved was measured at various time intervals and also after complete decomposition of H_2O_2 using a gas burette³⁰. Experiments were carried out at different temperatures in the range 25–40°. The influence of quantity of the complex bound to zirconium tungstate (0.025–0.075 g) was studied at 35°. The effect of variation of the concentration of H_2O_2 was also studied at 35°.

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